

CREEP STUDY OF FRP COMPOSITE REBARS FOR CONCRETE

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SUMMARY: Fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP) rebars, long rods produced by the “pultrusion” process and containing by volume about 55% E-glass fiber and about 45% thermoset resin, have been successfully applied as concrete reinforcement in many construction applications. However, creep, fatigue, and corrosion from alkaline environment of concrete are areas of concern for any large-scale application. In this investigation the creep study was limited to determine whether the commercially available FRP rebars would creep under a sustained tensile load over a wide range of temperatures: low temperature (−23°C, −10°F), room temperature (21°C, 70°F), and high temperature (49°C, 120°F). Because these rebars have fibers generally oriented in the longitudinal direction 12.70, 15.88 and 19.05 mm (1/2, 5/8, and 3/4 in.), the load would be carried primarily by the fibers. Six FRP rebars in nominal diameters with a spirally wrapped glass fiber strand were instrumented with strain gages to measure both the longitudinal and diametral strains under dead weight loads adjusted to tension each of these rebars to about 50 percent of its yield stress. In order to monitor temperatures, a thermocouple was attached to each rebar. For the room temperature tests, strain was measured for 1800 hours (75 days) and over this period the strain did not show any trend to continue to increase. The low temperature tests was continued for 3,552 hours and again no discernible trend of increasing strain was observed. The high temperature test was performed for 3,792 hours (158 days). From the creep data in which a very small trend of increasing strain could be observed, the values of creep parameters m and n were determined as $m = 9.45$, and $n = 0.297$. These values closely match with published values for commercially available pultruded FRP WF beams.

KEYWORDS: creep, composites, low temperature, FRP, polymer composites, sustained load, viscoelastic materials

INTRODUCTION

In recent times, FRP reinforcing bars are receiving increasing attention as the tension element in reinforced concrete [1]. This is primarily because corrosion of steel reinforcement in concrete by chloride ions has been determined to be the major cause of premature deterioration of concrete structures [2]. As available in market, these rebars, as long rods, are made of very fine continuous glass fiber strands which are bound together with a thermosetting polymer. Wu et al. [3] have reported that E-glass reinforced composite rods, from which these rebars are made, may have tensile strength in excess of 689 MPa (10^5 psi) and longitudinal elastic modulus about 51.7 GPa (7.5×10^6 psi). In tensile tests the bars fail without any significant yield (brittle failure).

Table 1. Comparison of mechanical properties of steel and FRP rebars [4].

Properties	Steel rebar	FRP rebar
Specific gravity	7.9	1.5– 2.0
Tensile strength MPa (psi × 10 ³)	483–690 (70–100)	517–1207 (75–175)
Yield strength MPa (psi × 10 ³)	276–414 (40–60)	—
Compressive strength MPa (psi × 10 ³)	276–414 (40–60)	310–482 (45–70)
Tensile modulus, GPa (psi × 10 ⁶)	200 (29)	41–55 (5.9–8.0)
Coeff. thermal expansion 10–6/°C (°F)	11.7 (6.5)	9.9 (5.5)

The rods are produced by pultrusion process. Since glass is commonly used as the reinforcing fibers in these rebars, these rebars are also designated as GFRP (G stands for glass). Currently there are several FRP rebar companies actively marketing their products in the USA. Most FRP rebars contain by volume about 55 percent E-glass fiber and about 45 percent thermoset resin. The sizes (diameter) of the rebars follow the size designations of the steel rebars (e.g., #3, #4, or #7 rebars). Faza [4] has reported a number of successful applications of rebars in the USA, including applications in sea walls, hospital magnetic resonance imagers (MRIs), reactor pads, compass calibration pads, mill roofs, laser test facilities, highway barriers, residential foundations, and bridge decks. Table 1 gives a comparison of mechanical properties of the steel rebars and the FRP rebars.

The light weight, corrosion resistant and nonmagnetic properties make the FRP rebars an improved alternative to steel. One of the most critical problems to be overcome in large-scale applications of the FRP rebars is developing improved bond strength with concrete. Some available designs provide a helically convex surface made with a strand spirally wound and cured on the surface. Other designs suggest use of sand or grit coating on the rebars. A recent design includes a pultruded ribbed surface. A comparative survey of the bond quality of these surface modifications is still not available. Bond strength of composite rebars and the bending response for carrying concrete stresses had been investigated by many including GangaRao and Faza [5], Pleimann [6], Daniali [7], Larralde and Siva [8], Iyer and Anigol [9], Tao et al. [10], Challal and Benmokrane [11], Challal and Benmokrane [12], and Malavar [13].

There are several major barriers to FRP rebar applications. These include lack of sufficient data on durability or performance under extreme environments [14, 15). Creep, fatigue, and corrosion from the alkaline environment of concrete are the areas of concern for any large-scale application of FRP rebars. Unlike steel the FRP rebar is viewed as a viscoelastic material, and, as such, many of its properties are suspected to be time dependent. Creep refers to the slow deformation with time under a constant stress which is less than the yield stress. When a constant load is applied (except for a short initial duration when the strain may increase quite rapidly) to a viscoelastic material, the strain increases steadily. This increase of strain is the creep. If the creep increases beyond a certain limit, the effective stress owing to decrease in cross-section area increases. The increased stress results in further deformation, which in turn increases the stress even more. Thus, the deformation suddenly accelerates, leading to the failure of the material.

At the microstructural level the creep occurs due to the presence of mobile defects, such as dislocations that move (enlarge) primarily at increased stress and temperatures. Thus the general mathematical formulation of creep rate takes the form

$$d\epsilon/dt = F(\sigma, T) \tag{1}$$

where ϵ is the strain, t is time variable, and $F(\sigma, T)$ is the function of the stress σ , and temperature T .

In the case of composites, F is a function of the stresses produced in all the components, since the net creep resistance will depend on the creep resistance of all the components. If the two components of the composites have two different creep resistance, the creep of the low resistance component will be checked by the high resistance material owing to adhesion between them. Thus, with higher bond strength between the components a creep resistance even greater than that of its components should result.

Creep in polymeric composites has been the subject of investigation for a long time [16, 17]. Tunik and Tomashevskii [18] discussed creep and long time strength of glass FRP in interlaminar shear. Weidmann and Ogorkiewicz [19] studied tensile creep of a unidirectional glass fiber epoxy laminate. Creep strength of discontinuous fiber composite has also been studied by Bocker-Pedersen [20]. The power law approach to modeling the creep behavior of plastics and FRP is primarily due to the original work by Findley [21] which he again updated in 1987 [22]. Numerous other projects have also been reported in composites literature about creep behavior of FRP in general. These include the work by Holmes and Rahman [23] on creep in FRP beams. Brinson et al. [24], Hiel and Brinson [25], and Dillard and Brinson [26] used numerical methods of predicting creep and delayed failures. Transverse creep and tensile behavior of composite laminates were studied by Eggleston [27], whereas Huang and Gibson [28] performed both theoretical and experimental studies on sandwich beams with linear viscoelastic cores. Creep behavior of Kevlar/epoxy composites was studied by Beckwith [29], who concluded that the creep behavior in the laminate composites is primarily “fiber-dominated,” and independent of resin modulus. Krishnaswamy et al. [30] presented the results of a finite element model of ductile behavior of polymers. The creep effects in composite columns were studied by Chen and Lottman [31], Ueng [32], and Vinogradov [32]. Slattery [34] developed the procedure for predicting the accelerated failure rate by extrapolating short-term data and by taking into consideration the progression of fundamental damage mechanism. Recently, Mossalam and Bank [35], and Mossalam and Chambers [36] presented a simplified and efficient design procedure to predict deflection of pultruded composites under sustained load and a laboratory procedure for determining the creep coefficients. Thus, while a large volume of information is available on the creep characteristics of the FRP materials in general, the specific information on whether the FRP rebars would creep or not under sustained loading is very scant.

In this investigation the scope of the creep study was limited to determine whether the commercially available FRP rebars would creep under a sustained tensile load over a wide range of temperatures: low temperature (-23°C , -10°F), room temperature (21°C , 70°F), and high temperature (49°C , 120°F). Because these rebars have fibers generally oriented in the longitudinal direction, the load would be carried primarily by the fibers.

TEST DESCRIPTION

Commercially available fiberglass composite rebars (Fig. 1) made with 5- to 10-micron E-glass fibers in a polyester resin matrix were selected for this creep study. The mechanical characteristics of these bars as provided by the manufacturer is given in Table 2.

To conduct the creep tests, the deadweight creep test fixture shown in Fig. 2 was designed and fabricated. The gripping mechanism is shown in Fig. 3. The fixture provides a mechanical advantage of approximately 50 to 1. Six of these creep-test fixtures were mounted on a common base frame (Fig. 4).

Fig. 1: Examples of commercially available glass fiber reinforced composite rebars.

Initially six fiberglass composite rebars made by a vendor were selected for the tests. The rebars were obtained in 12.70, 15.88, and 19.05 mm (1/2, 5/8, and 3/4 in.) nominal diameters with a spirally wrapped glass fiber strand, wound approximately 19.05 mm (3/4 in.) in pitch. The entire rod was redipped in the resin and then cured to obtain an irregular wavy but drip surface to promote adhesion to the concrete. For fixing on the test jigs the 19.05-mm (3/4-in.) diameter rebar specimen proved to be the most difficult one to be gripped and was finally rejected from the test batch. Only 12.70-mm and 15.88-mm (1/2-in and 5/8-in.) diameter bars were finally tested.

Each composite rebar was instrumented with electrical foil strain gages to measure both the longitudinal and diametrical strains (Fig. 5). Only longitudinal strains were of interest in this creep study. The gages were centrally located along the length of each specimen and diametrically opposite to each other. Each longitudinal gage was axially aligned with the fiber direction and positioned so as not to interfere with the spiral wrapping of the rebar. They had an effective length of 1.58 mm (0.062 in.), 350-ohm resistance, and were temperature compensated for steel. The gages were bonded to the rebar surface according to the manufacturer's recommended procedure. To avoid modifying the rebar specimen resin, as per the gage manufacturer's instructions, the gages were cured overnight at room temperature. No elevated temperature curing was attempted. For measuring strain, each gage was put in full bridge configuration and initially balanced in a switching and balancing unit. All subsequent readings were referenced to this initial balance.

Fig. 2: Deadweight creep test fixture.

Table 2. Mechanical characteristics of composite rebars.

Density	1.85 g/cm ³ (0.067 lb/in. ³)
Ultimate tensile strength	117.9 MPa (17,098 psi)
Tensile modulus	54.206 GPa (7.86 × 10 ⁶ psi)
Coefficient of therm. exp.	9.9 × 10 ⁻⁶ mm/mm/°C (5.5 × 10 ⁻⁶ in./in./°F)
Matrix	Derakane 411-45 polyester resin
Fiber	E-glass
Spiral fiber pitch	0.75 in. (190.5 mm)

The deadweights were adjusted to tension of each of these rebars to about 50 percent of its ultimate strength, as specified by manufacturer of the rebars. In order to monitor temperatures, a thermocouple was attached to each rebar. Once the tension for the rebar was fixed, the apparatus was not disturbed. For the room temperature tests, temperature and strain readings were taken once a day for 1800 hours (75 days). The strain data are shown in Fig. 6a and b for the 12.70 mm (1/2 in.) and 15.88 mm (5/8 in.) bar, respectively. If any creep occurred, then the strain readings would be expected to continue to increase. However, the results show that over this period the strain did not indicate any trend to increase. The temperature variation of the room in which the test fixture was placed caused the daily variation of the strain as seen by the zigzag lines of the record, but the general trend did not reveal development of any creep under the test conditions.

If no creep could be detected at room temperature, then we should not expect any creep to occur at low temperature (-23°C, -10°F). However, creep might result if the low temperature induces any microcracking or degradation of the interface bond by the induced thermal

stresses from the thermal expansion coefficient mismatch between fibers and matrix. A relatively longer period of test was necessary to develop these effects. Accordingly the dead weight test fixture was placed in a refrigerated coldroom where the temperature was constantly maintained at approximately -10°C (-23°F). This test was continued for 3,552 hours (148 days). The strain records of the 12.70-mm (1/2-in.) and 15.88-mm (5/8-in.) rebars are shown in Fig. 7a and b. Again no discernible trend of increasing strain was observed.

Fig. 3: Details of the gripping mechanism of the creep test fixture

For high temperature (120°F , 49°C) creep test a special environment chamber of $1.22 \times 1.22 \times 2.44$ m ($4 \times 4 \times 8$ ft) was built with a thermostatically controlled hot air blowing system that would control the temperature of the chamber between 50°C (122°F) and 47.2°C (117°F). At the end of the coldroom test, the strain gages on the 15.88 mm (5/8 in.) rebars were damaged and the bars were unsuitable for further testing. Accordingly only two 12.70 mm (1/2 in.) diameter rebars were tested in the high temperature chamber. Each of these specimens were instrumented with a thermocouple sensor, and a third thermocouple measured the air temperature of the chamber near the specimens. These specimens were subjected to again for a long period of test, from 25 April to 30 September, a total of 3,792 hours (158 days). The strain readings taken approximately once a week were remarkably steady over this period. The numerical data recorded for this test are shown in table 16. Fig. 8a and b gives the plotted data.

Fig. 4: Creep test platform with six creep test fixtures.

Fig. 5: Strain gage instrumentation on the test specimens. Test specimens shown removed from the test fixture after the test is over.

Fig. 6: Records of room temperature creep strain at (a) 12.70 mm (1/2 in.) diameter rebar, and (b) 15.88 mm (5/8 in.) diameter rebar.

Fig. 7: Records of low temperature (-10°F , -23°C) creep strain at (a) 12.70 (1/2 in.) diameter rebar, and (b) 15.88 mm (5/8 in.) diameter rebar.

Fig. 8: Records of high temperature (49°C , 120°F) creep strain at (a) 12.70 mm (1/2 in.) diameter rebar, and (b) 15.88 mm (5/8 in.) diameter rebar.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Findley's general theory [21] of creep behavior of viscoelastic polymer is represented by

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_0 + p (t/t_0)^q \quad (2)$$

where ε = the total strain

ε_0 = stress dependent strain

p = the coefficient of time dependent term, which is dependent on stress level

t = duration of loading (hours)

t_0 = unit time (hour)

q = a material constant, independent of stress.

Parameters p , and q are known as creep parameters. To obtain the particular values of p and q Eqn 2 can be rearranged and written in the form:

$$\log (\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0) = \log (p) + q \log (t/t_0) \quad (3)$$

Table 3. FRP rebar creep test data at 49°C (120°F).

Date	Chamber temp (°F)	Microstrain* in rebar no.5	Microstrain* in rebar no. 6
04/25/94	120	1209	1281
05/02/94	120	1209	1273
05/09/94	119	1220	1279
05/16/94	119	1221	1274
05/23/94	120	1216	1273
06/01/94	120	1218	1276
06/07/94	120	1220	1270
06/15/94	119	1222	1276
06/22/94	121	1211	1268
07/01/94	119	1215	1269
07/05/94	121	1220	1272
07/06/94	122	1220	1272
07/07/94	121	1215	1272
07/15/94	121	1218	1275
07/21/94	118	1213	1273
08/01/94	119	1217	1268
08/08/94	118	1216	1272
08/15/94	121	1221	1276
08/22/94	121	1223	1277
09/01/94	122	1219	1276
09/07/94	122	1221	1276
09/15/94	120	1221	1271
09/20/94	121	1221	1271
09/30/94	118	1216	1262

*microstrain = strain $\times 10^{-6}$

Equation 3 represents a straight line of slope n and intercept m at unit time if $\log(\epsilon - \epsilon_0)$ is plotted against $\log(t/t_0)$. Using the creep data of Table 3, in which a very small trend of increasing strain could be observed, the values of m and n were determined as $p = 9.45$, and $q = 0.297$. These values closely match Mosallam and Chamber's [36] published values for commercially available pultruded FRP WF beams: $p = 9.72$, and $q = 0.298$. Findley's equation, when plotted over the Table 3 data points as shown in Fig. 9, but the match is not very clear because of the scatter in the data. If the tests were continued over a longer time, a more discernible creep strain might have developed. The data at room temperature and low temperature had not shown any trend of increasing; therefore they were not analyzed with Findley's equation. It must be noted that Findley's theory applies very well to viscoelastic polymers, but in FRC composites rebars, when the stress is applied in the fiber direction, the behavior is not totally viscoelastic. In fact, with higher volume fraction of glass fibers oriented in loading direction creep in FRP composites is not expected to be a problem.

Fig. 9: Comparison of high temperature creep data with Findley's equation.

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